

Anesthetic Management in a Patient with Wolff-Parkinson-White Syndrome Undergoing Radical Nephrectomy: A Case Report

Rafael Alejandro Saldaña Rentería*¹, Daniel Alejandro Castillo Moreno², Giselle Margarita Pech Estrella³

¹Third-year Anesthesiology Resident, High Specialty Regional Hospital of the Yucatan Peninsula, Facultad de Medicina, Universidad Autónoma de Yucatán, Mérida, Mexico.

²Adjunct Professor, Department of Anesthesiology, High Specialty Regional Hospital of the Yucatan Peninsula, Mérida, Mexico.

³Third-year Anesthesiology Resident, "Lic. Ignacio García Téllez" Regional General Hospital, Facultad de Medicina, Universidad Autónoma de Yucatán, Mérida, Mexico.

ABSTRACT

Patients with Wolff-Parkinson-White (WPW) Syndrome present a significant challenge when undergoing anesthetic procedures, as there is always a latent risk of life-threatening arrhythmias triggered by surgical stimuli, perioperative stress, or even during anesthetic induction and emergence. We present the case of a 53-year-old patient with a recent diagnosis of WPW, demonstrating a characteristic "Delta Wave" on electrocardiography and associated symptoms of precordial pain and palpitations, in whom a potentially malignant renal tumor was incidentally discovered during imaging evaluation. Given the inherent risk of tumor progression and metastatic disease, surgical intervention was prioritized by a multidisciplinary team after careful cardiovascular risk assessment. The patient underwent a Simple Radical Nephrectomy without having previously received accessory pathway ablation via electrophysiological intervention. The anesthetic management focused on the careful selection of drugs with low arrhythmogenic potential, antiarrhythmic properties, strict hemodynamic and electrocardiographic monitoring, and the availability of antiarrhythmic agents and synchronized electrical cardioversion in the operating room. The procedure resulted in a favorable and uneventful perioperative outcome despite the elevated risk of developing tachyarrhythmias.

KEYWORDS: Wolff-Parkinson-White, anesthesia, nephrectomy, case report.

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INTRODUCTION

Wolff-Parkinson-White Syndrome is a rare, congenital heart condition, affecting 1 to 3 people per thousand globally (0.1–3.1%) [1,2]. It involves one or multiple accessory atrioventricular conduction pathways, predisposing the patient to potentially malignant tachyarrhythmias. There is a fundamental difference between a WPW Pattern and a WPW Syndrome: most individuals with a WPW Pattern are often asymptomatic and do not experience clinical events related to the accessory pathway. In contrast, WPW Syndrome often presents with symptoms like palpitations, dizziness,

shortness of breath, presyncope, and syncope (often the symptom prompting patients to seek medical care), but in rare cases, the first sign or symptom is sudden cardiac death due to a malignant tachyarrhythmia [1, 3].

The anesthetic approach involves additional risks, as sympathomimetic drugs, certain anesthetics, and surgical maneuvers can precipitate arrhythmias by accelerating conduction through the accessory pathways [2]. Therefore, the reviewed literature suggests using drugs that decrease the risk of arrhythmias and prolong the refractory period of the accessory pathways [2,5].

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Major surgery, such as nephrectomy, presents a challenge due to the potential for bleeding, hemodynamic changes (due to patient positioning, secondary to anesthetics, volume loss from bleeding), and the prolonged duration of the surgical procedure [4,6]. Consequently, for elective surgery, it is typically preferred to delay the procedure until the patient has received electrophysiology therapy [2]. However, given the high suspicion of a malignancy and the fact that only 15% of renal tumors are benign, the necessity of the procedure elevated its status to an urgent oncological procedure [4].

CASE REPORT

We present the case of a 53-year-old female patient, originally from Yucatán, a housewife, of low socioeconomic status, presenting with a history of precordial pain and palpitations. These symptoms occurred sporadically and remitted with rest. She had a recent diagnosis of Wolff-Parkinson-White Syndrome, managed medically with Bisoprolol 1.25 mg every 24 hours, and was currently being evaluated for accessory pathway ablation. A CT scan revealed a tumor lesion with irregular borders in the lower pole of the right kidney. She was scheduled for an Open Right Radical Nephrectomy under General Anesthesia.

On physical examination, her blood pressure (BP) was 127/64 mmHg. Three ECGs showed a short PR interval (116 ms) and the presence of "delta waves" suggestive of WPW syndrome (Figure 1), combined with the presence of symptoms (chest pain and palpitations). The 2D Transthoracic Echocardiogram found valves with normal characteristics and mobility, as well as normal ventricular sizes, and an LVEF of 66% by the biplane Simpson method, ruling out possible associated abnormalities of the syndrome. Preoperative laboratory tests showed a serum creatinine level of 0.95 mg/dL with a GFR reduction to 68.4 mL/min by CKD-EPI, with no contraindications for the surgical procedure.

ANESTHETIC MANAGEMENT

A pre-anesthetic evaluation was performed, establishing an ASA physical status 3, a Revised Cardiac Risk Index (RCRI) Class I, and an ACS NSQIP cardiac complication risk of 0.4%. The anesthetic plan proposed General Anesthesia with Invasive Monitoring. Antiarrhythmic

drugs and a Defibrillator were available in the operating room.

Upon arrival in the operating room, monitoring included non-invasive blood pressure (NIBP), Bispectral Index (BIS) with spectrogram, Pulse Oximetry, 5-lead ECG, and Neuromuscular Monitoring (DRAEGER Infinity Trident). The patient's heart rate (HR) was 89 bpm and BP was 130/68 mmHg.

Two Target-Controlled Infusion (TCI) systems (HP TCI Pro, Medcaptain, China) were used with the pharmacokinetic models of Shafer [7] and Eleveld [8] for fentanyl and propofol, respectively. Induction was initiated simultaneously with a Target Effect-Site Concentration (Ce) of Fentanyl at 4 ng/mL and Propofol at 1.5 µg/mL, followed by Rocuronium 0.6 mg/kg. After confirming an adequate anesthetic depth (BIS 45–50, TOF 0), Video Laryngoscopy was performed using a hyper-curved blade (POGO 100%). A 7.0 mm Endotracheal Tube with a cuff was inserted, resulting in minimal hemodynamic changes (HR 60–80 bpm; BP 125–110/80–60 mmHg) during the process. A right jugular central venous catheter was placed using ultrasound guidance, and Invasive Blood Pressure was monitored via the Right Radial artery.

Anesthesia was maintained with Desflurane at 0.6 MAC, maintaining the BIS level between 40–60. Fentanyl infusion was maintained at a Target Effect-Site Concentration (Ce) of 2 ng/mL, and Propofol at 1 µg/mL in effect site concentrations, and a Dexmedetomidine infusion was initiated at 0.2 µg/kg/h. Adjuvant medications administered included Ondansetron 4 mg IV, Dexamethasone 4 mg IV, Tranexamic Acid 1 g IV, and Acetaminophen 1 g IV.

The surgical procedure was carried out without incident. Residual neuromuscular blockade was reversed with Sugammadex, performing a deep or "asleep" extubation. After recovering consciousness (BIS >90), the patient was transferred to the post-anesthesia care unit for surveillance.

Postoperative management included PONV prophylaxis, scheduled IV Acetaminophen for analgesia, and rescue doses of IV Buprenorphine. The patient was discharged on the second day post-surgery. The histopathology report described a Fuhrman 2, pT3a N0 clear cell renal carcinoma.

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Figure 1. Preoperative 12-lead electrocardiogram demonstrating sinus rhythm with a shortened PR interval and the presence of a delta wave (highlighted), consistent with ventricular pre-excitation in Wolff-Parkinson-White syndrome.

DISCUSSION

The anesthetic management of a patient with Wolff-Parkinson-White (WPW) Syndrome requiring major surgery, such as radical nephrectomy, always poses a significant challenge. The main concern is the high risk of arrhythmias that can occur during the surgical procedure. Most literature recommends delaying the procedure until the patient has undergone accessory pathway ablation [1,2,3]. In this case, the high suspicion of a malignant renal neoplasm (85% of solid renal tumors) [4] made the surgery a priority. This meant we had to design a completely tailored anesthetic strategy to manage the risk.

The intraoperative anesthetic approach was divided into three specific phases. The goals for perioperative management included continuing beta-blocker treatment [2,9], minimizing hemodynamic changes and sympathetic nervous system response, and avoiding anticholinergic agents to prevent triggering an intraoperative tachyarrhythmia. Antiarrhythmic drugs and a defibrillator were made readily available in the operating room [2,9,10,11].

Anesthetic Induction

We planned the indispensable use of advanced monitoring (BIS, neuromuscular monitoring, invasive blood pressure) [10,11]. We relied on TCI systems to administer a combination of Propofol and opioids (Fentanyl) due to their effects of increasing the refractoriness of the accessory pathways by blocking sodium/calcium channels [2, 5, 12, 13]. We also employed Dexmedetomidine, whose sympatholytic effect has been shown to reduce perioperative tachyarrhythmias and actively contribute to cardiovascular stability [2, 12]. The

choice of Desflurane was considered safe, especially when maintaining a low MAC (0.6). Rocuronium was selected for Neuromuscular Relaxation, with the availability of Sugammadex providing a vital safety margin [2]. Video Laryngoscopy was chosen to minimize the hemodynamic changes produced during laryngoscopy [14,15].

Maintenance

Propofol and Fentanyl in TCI mode, Desflurane, and Dexmedetomidine, combined with neuromonitoring (BIS), allowed us to maintain an adequate anesthetic level with minimal hemodynamic alterations. Acetaminophen was administered [16], while Non-Steroidal Anti-inflammatory Drugs (NSAIDs) were avoided due to their potential to increase bleeding risk [20]. Tranexamic Acid was used to reduce the risk of bleeding and the inherent changes that hypovolemia can cause [17].

Emergence and Postoperative Period

A deep or "asleep" extubation was chosen to minimize the secondary hemodynamic changes that can occur during this process [18, 19]. Postoperative management included PONV prophylaxis and scheduled IV Acetaminophen with rescue doses of IV Buprenorphine [16].

We attribute the success to the proactive anticipation of potential complications, the thorough review, and the comprehensive, multidisciplinary planning of the approach. The main limitation we faced was the absence of prior accessory pathway ablation, which always presented a latent risk factor.

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CONCLUSION

This case demonstrates that the presence of WPW syndrome, a potentially fatal condition, coupled with a non-deferrable oncological necessity, requires a multidisciplinary approach and the use of an individualized anesthetic strategy utilizing available resources to maintain strict control over the sympathetic response during the most critical perioperative moments, thereby achieving a favorable outcome despite the lack of prior ablation.

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Conflicts of Interest: None.

Ethical Considerations: The patient was informed at all times about the diagnosis, interventions performed, and potential risks. Written informed consent was obtained for the surgical and anesthetic procedures, as well as for the publication of this case report, in accordance with the ethical principles of the Declaration of Helsinki and the institutional regulations of the hospital.

REFERENCES

- I. Barat, M., Barba, D. T., & Ho, G. (2025). Wolff-Parkinson-White syndrome: Diagnostic and management strategies. *Cleveland Clinic Journal of Medicine*, 92(2), 119–127. <https://doi.org/10.3949/ccjm.92a.24059>
- II. Staikou, C., Stamelos, M., & Stavroulakis, E. (2018). Perioperative management of patients with pre-excitation syndromes. *Romanian Journal of Anaesthesia and Intensive Care*, 25(2), 131–147. <https://doi.org/10.21454/rjaic.7518.252.stk>
- III. Kulig, J., & Koplan, B. A. (2010). Wolff-Parkinson-White syndrome and accessory pathways. *Circulation*, 122(15), e480–e483. <https://doi.org/10.1161/CIRCULATIONAHA.109.929372>
- IV. Bex, A., Ghanem, Y. A., Albiges, L., et al. (2025). European Association of Urology guidelines on renal cell carcinoma: The 2025 update. *European Urology*, 87(6), 683–696. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eururo.2025.02.020>
- V. Liu, Q., Kong, A. L., Chen, R., et al. (2011). Propofol and arrhythmias: Two sides of the coin. *Acta Pharmacologica Sinica*, 32(6), 817–823. <https://doi.org/10.1038/aps.2011.42>
- VI. Liu, Z., Zhao, X., Zhang, H. X., et al. (2020). Peking University Third Hospital score: A comprehensive system to predict intra-operative blood loss in radical nephrectomy and thrombectomy. *Chinese Medical Journal*, 133(10), 1166–1174. <https://doi.org/10.1097/CM9.0000000000000799>
- VII. Shafer, S. L., Varvel, J. R., Aziz, N., & Scott, J. C. (1990). Pharmacokinetics of fentanyl administered by computer-controlled infusion pump. *Anesthesiology*, 73(6), 1091–1102. <https://doi.org/10.1097/0000542-199012000-00005>
- VIII. Eleveld, D. J., Colin, P., Absalom, A. R., & Struys, M. M. R. F. (2018). Pharmacokinetic-pharmacodynamic model for propofol for broad application in anaesthesia and sedation. *British Journal of Anaesthesia*, 120(5), 942–959. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bja.2018.01.018>
- IX. Stewart, A. M., Greaves, K., & Bromilow, J. (2015). Supraventricular tachyarrhythmias and their management in the perioperative period. *Continuing Education in Anaesthesia Critical Care & Pain*, 15(2), 90–97. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bjaceaccp/mku018>
- X. Halvorsen, S., Mehilli, J., Cassese, S., et al. (2022). ESC guidelines on cardiovascular assessment and management of patients undergoing non-cardiac surgery. *European Heart Journal*, 43(39), 3826–3924. <https://doi.org/10.1093/eurheartj/ehac270>
- XI. Thompson, A., Fleischmann, K. E., Smilowitz, N. R., et al. (2024). AHA/ACC/ACS/ASNC/HRS/SCA/SCCT/SCMR/VM guideline for perioperative cardiovascular management for noncardiac surgery. *Circulation*, 150(19), e351–e442. <https://doi.org/10.1161/CIR.0000000000001285>
- XII. Peng, J., Wu, Y., Li, L., et al. (2024). Dexmedetomidine vs. propofol on arrhythmia in cardiac surgery: A meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *Frontiers in Cardiovascular Medicine*, 11, 1433841. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fcvm.2024.1433841>
- XIII. Gupta, A., Sharma, J., Banerjee, N., & Sood, R. (2013). Anesthetic management in a patient with Wolff-Parkinson-White syndrome for laparoscopic cholecystectomy. *Anesthesia: Essays and Researches*, 7(2), 270–272. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0259-1162.118988>
- XIV. Wang, L., Li, H., Zhong, Y., et al. (2024). Comparative analysis of hemodynamic responses and oropharyngeal complications in tracheal intubation. *Medical Science Monitor*, 30, e944916. <https://doi.org/10.12659/MSM.944916>

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- XV. Apfelbaum, J. L., Hagberg, C. A., Connis, R. T., et al. (2022). American Society of Anesthesiologists practice guidelines for management of the difficult airway. *Anesthesiology*, 136(1), 31–81. <https://doi.org/10.1097/ALN.0000000000004002>
- XVI. Koh, W., Nguyen, K. P., & Jahr, J. S. (2015). Intravenous non-opioid analgesia for peri- and postoperative pain management. *Korean Journal of Anesthesiology*, 68(1), 3–12. <https://doi.org/10.4097/kjae.2015.68.1.3>
- XVII. Kim, J., Alrumaih, A., Donnelly, C., et al. (2023). The impact of tranexamic acid on perioperative outcomes in urological surgeries: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Canadian Urological Association Journal*, 17(6), 205–216. <https://doi.org/10.5489/cuaj.8254>
- XVIII. Juang, J., Cordoba, M., Ciaramella, A., et al. (2020). Incidence of airway complications associated with deep extubation in adults. *BMC Anesthesiology*, 20(1), 274. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12871-020-01191-8>
- XIX. Lee, M. A., Schenke, P. W., Faller, M. R., DeYoung, H. R., & Adams, A. R. (2025). A comparison of deep versus awake tracheal extubation in adults. *BMC Anesthesiology*, 25(1), 387. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12871-025-03224-6>
- XX. Bongiovanni, T., Lancaster, E., Ledesma, Y., et al. (2021). Association between non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs and operative bleeding in the perioperative period. *Journal of the American College of Surgeons*, 232(5), 765–790. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jamcollsurg.2021.01.005>